

Hepatitis B Knowledge and Risk Perceptions among undergraduate students at the University of Calabar, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection caused 1.34million deaths in 2015, a number comparable to deaths caused by tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS combined. Previous prevalence of HBV was estimated to be 12.2%. **Objective:** This study aimed to determine Hepatitis B knowledge and risk perceptions among undergraduates of University of Calabar. **Method:** A cross-sectional descriptive study design was used and data were collected from 794 respondents using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire. **Results:** The majority, 727 (91.6%) have heard about HBV, 678 (85.4%) correctly picked virus as cause of HBV, while 81(10.2%) picked malaria and consumption of dirty untreated water as the causes of HBV infection. On the mode of transmission, 598(75.3%) correctly picked sexual intercourse, 462(58.2%) picked sharing of sharp objects with infected persons. The majority, 562(70.8%) had good knowledge about the vaccines, while 232(29.9%) have poor knowledge, 506(63.7%) perceive HBV infection as treatable, 42(35.3%) respondents perceived HBV infection to be the same as HIV/AIDS, 615(77.4%) perceived it to be preventable, while 397(50.6%) respondents identified transfusion of unscreened blood as a risk factor for transmission of HBV. Summarily, 99(12.4%) respondents had poor knowledge, 213(26.8%) had moderate knowledge and 482(60.8%) students had good knowledge about Hepatitis B virus. Only half of the respondents, 398(50.2%) perceived HBV infection as a serious infection while 136(17.1%) have low perceived severity. **Conclusion:** Low perceived severity of HBV in a young, sexually active population may fuel increased prevalence if nothing is done to mitigate it. On-campus social marketing campaigns encouraging testing and preventive practices are recommended.

Keywords: Hepatitis B virus, knowledge, perceptions, risk, undergraduates

Introduction

Public health activities to control viral hepatitis have progressively increased over the past three decades. In the 1990s, the World Health Assembly first recommended the inclusion of the hepatitis B vaccine in routine infant immunization schedules (Loharikar et al. 2016). Hepatitis B vaccine given shortly after birth prevents HBV infection that occurs early in life. HBV infection acquired during infancy carries a greater risk of death later in life from cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (Wu and Chang 2015). The coverage of immunization against HBV increased from the early 2000s with support from the Vaccine Alliance (World Health Organization 2017). From the 2000s, finding from the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) project increased the certainty of the correct estimates for the real burden of deaths that occur as a result of viral

hepatitis (World Health Organization 2017). However, it became a fact that cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma accounted for the majority of the disease burden from viral hepatitis. Innovative prevention approaches were developed over time. These approaches included blood screening, injection safety, control of infection, and prevention of transmission of hepatitis in people who inject drugs (PWID) (World Health Organization 2017). Ikobah et al. (2016) stated that over 300 million people have chronic liver infections globally and about 0.2% of people die annually from acute or chronic complications from HBV. The highest prevalence of this disease has been reported in Sub-Saharan Africa and East Asia. The pooled prevalence of HBV in Nigeria from a 13 year study is 13.6% (Ikobah et al. 2016). This prevalence data vary by screening method used with immunochromatography yielding the highest prevalence (17.5%) (Ikobah et al. 2016).

The World Health Organization (2017) reported that early interventions for the treatment and management of viral hepatitis B and C had limited effectiveness and were less cost-effective. This showed that there was poor progress in the management of people infected with chronic hepatitis. Improved awareness of the virus grew by 2010 and was impeded by the poor response, which further led to increased mortality due to hepatitis. In 2010, the World Health Assembly facilitated the establishment of the WHO's Global Hepatitis Program in 2011 (World Health Organization 2017). Further research and development facilitated the new revolutionary treatments for HCV infection, which led to better health outcomes. In 2014, further resolution highlighted the public health importance of viral hepatitis and in turn stirred up a greater likelihood of eliminating HBV and HCV (World Health Organization 2017).

Hepatitis B, a small enveloped DNA virus (Mason et al. 2016), formerly referred to as 'serum hepatitis' is transmitted via contact with the blood or body fluids (saliva, sweat, semen, and vaginal fluid) of an infected person (Komatsu, Inui and Fujisawa 2016). Other risk factors for HBV infection include working in health care setting which poses the risk of needle prick injuries, contact with and transfusion of infected blood, dialysis, acupuncture, use of contaminated needles among PWIDs, sharing razor blade, tattooing, sharing toothbrushes which can breach the oral mucosa and migration into endemic locations (Kew 2010). Additionally, individuals exposed to other viral infections (Kew 2010) and subjected to unsafe practices such as local circumcision, scarification of the body, and piercing are at great risk of contracting HBV (Center for Disease Control and Prevention 2015).

Nigeria is highly endemic to HBV infection with over 70% of the population showing evidence of past infection of the virus (Olayinka et al. 2016). The average prevalence rate of HBV infection in Nigeria ranges between 11% and 13.7%. Joseph and Olokoba (2020) reported that the level of HBV infection was estimated to be 23 million. Also, Hwang and Cheung (2011) stated that there is little or no gender disparity in HBV infection because both sexes are almost equally affected, but young adults have been found to have a higher prevalence of infection. The ratio of HBV infection in Nigeria is estimated at one in every 8 persons and its prevalence is estimated to be 3 times more than HIV/AIDS (Joseph and Olokoba 2020).

A study carried out in Kano Nigeria in 2012 found that among 440 HIV positive patients, 12.3% were co-positive for HBV (Hamza et al. 2013). In southern Nigeria, 58.1% of patients with chronic liver disease were found to be positive for HBsAg (Ajide, Adogo and Omilabu 2016). Also, a systematic review of hepatitis B infection in Nigeria between 2000 and 2013 gave a pooled prevalence of hepatitis B in Nigeria as 13.6% (Musa et al. 2015).

Considering the dangers of the infection and its hyperendemicity in Nigeria, this study was conducted to assess Hepatitis B knowledge and preventive practices among undergraduates of the University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria. This also serves to promote awareness, and the information gathered can be used to develop a better and need-based program for the society.

Materials and Methods

Study setting

The University of Calabar (UNICAL) is located in Calabar formally known as Calabar kingdom but now Calabar Municipality and Calabar South. Calabar metropolis has a population ranging from 250,000-

499,999 inhabitants (UniRank 2020). UNICAL was once known as the Calabar Campus of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) until 1975 when it was made a campus on its own (University of Calabar 2021). It began academic activities as an autonomous institution in October 1976 with about 896 students and a staff strength of 156 (University of Calabar 2021). UNICAL is officially recognized by the National University Commission of Nigeria.

The male students of the University of Calabar are known as Malabites while the female students are known as Malabresses. The male hostel is generally referred to as Malabo republic; this was due to the challenges faced by students at the time which coincided with the suffering of Nigerian deportees in Malabo, Equatorial Guinea. The institution has an estimated population of 40,000-45,000 students (UniRank 2020). The University has one (1) graduate school, fifteen (15) faculties, and three (3) institutes. It offers recognized higher degrees such as Bachelor, Masters, and Doctor of Philosophy degrees. The institution is blessed with a rich cultural and gender diversity where students from all around the world are admitted and encouraged to live in peaceful coexistence. The University serves as a good setting for this study being that it inhabits people of diverse ages, races, and cultures. Hepatitis B can however affect any of these groups of persons and any point in time due to the tendency of young adults to indulge in unprotected sexual intercourse. Therefore, determining their attitude, behavior, and preventive practices towards Hepatitis B will add majorly to the body of knowledge.

Scope of the Study

This study was designed to understand Hepatitis B knowledge and risk perceptions among undergraduate students from selected faculties at the University of Calabar, Nigeria.

Study design

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study which employed a quantitative approach to determine the study outcomes.

Study Population

This study comprised of undergraduates of the University of Calabar regardless of their ages.

Sample size determination

The sample size was determined using the formula described by Yamane (1967) as follows:
$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where N = estimated study population (40,645); n = desired sample size; e = allowable error (%) = 0.05. This resulted in a minimum sample size of approximately 400. Assuming a non-response rate of 5% (0.05)

$$\text{Using: } n = \frac{N}{1-\text{Non-response rate}} = 421$$

Therefore, the total sample size was 421. However, the calculated sample was multiplied by 2 to account for the design effect, bringing the total sample size to 842.

Sampling procedure

A multistage sampling technique was used in selecting the faculties, departments, and respondents.

Stage 1: Selection of faculties.

Six (6) faculties were picked out of the fifteen (15) faculties in the University of Calabar using a simple random sampling technique. This was done in the form of a lottery whereby each faculty name was written on a piece of paper, folded, and then put in a basket. After being thoroughly shaken, six (6) pieces out of the fifteen were picked from the basket to represent the six (6) faculties which were used to carry out the study.

Stage 2: Selection of departments

Departments were selected using a simple random sampling procedure and the lottery method as used above in stage 1 was also employed in selecting three (3) departments from each faculty selected.

Stage 3: Selection of respondents.

From the eighteen (18) selected departments across the 6 faculties, students from 100 – 600 level were randomly selected. 47 students were randomly selected from each of the 18 departments. In each selected department, respondents who were in the study group were conveniently selected because they were available and willing to participate.

Instrument for data collection

A 33-item semi-structured questionnaire was developed based on the research objectives. The instruments consisted of 5 sections (A, B, C, D, and E) with 33 items. Section A: Consisted of socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Section B: Consisted of knowledge of Hepatitis B. Section C: Consisted of perceptions of Hepatitis B. Section D: Consisted of knowledge of risk factors associated with Hepatitis B. Section E: Consisted of Diagnosis and Treatment of Hepatitis B.

The instrument for data collection was pre-tested among undergraduates of Cross River State College of Health Technology, Calabar Campus by administering the questionnaire to 10 respondents (5% of the sample size). This was done to ascertain the validity and reliability of the instrument to be used for the data collection.

Pretesting of the Instrument

The instrument for data collection was pre-tested among undergraduates for College of Health Technology, Calabar campus using 10% of the total sample size. This was done to checkmate simplicity and ambiguity of the questions as well as the completion time for the instrument.

Method of data collection

The data was collected using both a self-administered questionnaire and an interviewer-administered questionnaire. The later was used because the researcher encountered respondents who were not willing to participate fully in the process because they could neither read nor write while the former was used because the researcher encountered respondents that were willing to participate fully in the process and could read and write. It was developed in the English language and it comprised open-ended and close-ended questions. The data was collected by the researcher with the help of three well-trained field assistants.

Ethical consideration

An approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Department of Public Health, University of Calabar, Nigeria (UC/CM/PUH/ETH/1970). The research participants were informed about the objectives of the project and consent was obtained after the provision of adequate and clear explanation. The study was however conducted in compliance with the 1978 Belmont Report on Ethical principles in human research.

Method of data analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed with the use of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics which includes; mean median, mode, standard deviations, and frequencies were determined for all continuous variables while frequencies were determined for categorical variables. Results were presented using tables.

Results

A total of 842 copies of questionnaires were distributed for the study, however, 794 were filled, returned, and used for the analysis, giving a response rate of 94.3%.

Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents

As presented in Table 1, there were 458(57.7%) male respondents and 336(42.3%) females who took part in the study. Majority of the respondents, 26.1% were between the ages of 24-27 years and those aged 36 and greater made up the least number of respondents (7.1%). Analyses of the marital status of the respondents showed that majority of the respondents (77.6%) were single and those who were widowed made up the least number of respondents (2.3%).

In terms of respondents' level of study, the analyses showed that majority of the respondents (28.5%) were in their 2nd year of study. Those in their 5th year made up the least number of respondents (11.2%). 90.6% of respondents practiced Christianity while 0.9% were of Eckankar belief, making up the least number of respondents based on religion.

Table 1: Social-demographic variables of respondents

n=794		
Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	458	57.7
Female	336	42.3
Age		
16-19	162	20.4
20-23	198	24.9
24-27	207	26.1
28-31	106	13.3
32-35	65	8.2
≥36	56	7.1
Marital status		
Single	616	77.6
Married	134	16.9
Divorced	26	3.3
Widowed	18	2.3
Level of study		
100	216	27.2
200	226	28.5
300	113	14.2
400	150	18.9
500	89	11.2
Religion		
Christian	720	90.6
Muslim	49	6.2
Traditional	18	2.3
Eckankar	7	0.9

Knowledge of Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection

As indicated in table 2 below, most of the respondents (91.6%) have heard about HBV. Schools (62.8%) were the major source of information for HBV by undergraduates while churches (27.2%) were the least source of information. Majority of the respondents (85.4%) identified a virus to be the causal agent for HBV while 10.2%, 3.3%, and 1.1% of the respondents identified malaria, dirty surroundings and untreated water respectively to be the causes of HBV. 53% of respondents identified jaundice as a major symptom of HBV. Condoms (71.4%) were the most identified method of preventing HBV and most respondents (76.4%) knew that HBV could lead to death. Also, majority of the respondents had good knowledge about the HBV

vaccine, only 43.6% had ever received it, and 22.4% of the respondents stated that their main reason for not getting the vaccine was because they were not aware of its existence.

Table 2: Knowledge of Hepatitis B virus infection

n=794		
Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Heard of HBV		
Yes	727	91.6
No	67	8.4
Information source		
Radio/TV	298	37.5
Family/friends	398	50.1
Church	216	27.2
School	499	62.8
Social/mass media	307	38.7
Causes of HBV		
Virus	678	85.4
Malaria	81	10.2
Dirty surroundings	26	3.3
Untreated water	09	1.1
Know HBV transmissible		
Contact	207	26.1
Sharing sharp objects	462	58.2
Sex intercourse	598	75.3
Eating together	64	8.1
Mother to child	377	47.5
Symptoms of HBV		
No symptoms	10	1.3
Sleeping	121	15.2
Fever	229	28.8
Laughing	17	2.1
Jaundice	421	53.0
Prevention of HBV		
Vaccination	462	58.2
Condom	568	71.4
Screened blood	379	47.7
Proper health waste disposal	509	64.1
HBV cause death		
Yes	607	76.4
No	185	23.3
Heard HBV vaccine		
Yes	562	70.8
No	232	29.2
Ever received an HBV vaccine		
Yes	346	43.6
No	299	37.6
Can't remember	249	18.8
Reasons for not receiving		
Not aware of vaccination	178	22.4
Not aware of vaccine site	106	13.3
It is expensive	69	8.7
Feel it's not useful	119	15.0
Fear of infection	86	10.8
Know who to be vaccinated		
Yes	612	77.1
No	182	22.9
Ever diagnosed of HBV		
Yes	78	9.8
No	716	90.1
Date of diagnosis		
1-2 month ago	16	2.0
3 months ago	21	2.6

Can't remember	41	5.2
Who diagnosed		
Doctor	60	7.6
Chemist	1	0.1
Laboratory scientist	17	2.1
Treatment given		
Injection	28	3.5
Vaccine	32	4.0
Drugs	18	2.3
Measures against reoccurrence		
Regular vaccine	15	1.9
Abstinence	24	3.0

*Multiple response allowed for variable 'Information source'

Perceptions of Hepatitis B virus infection

As shown in Table 3, the analysis revealed that most of the respondents (63.7%) perceived HBV infection to be treatable and 200 (25.2%) indicated HBV infection as one that is not treatable. About 569 (71.4%) respondents perceived that HBV infection can be gotten from sexual intercourse while 42(5.3%) respondents perceived HBV infection to be the same as HIV/AIDS.

Also, the majority of the respondents 615(77.4%) knew that HBV infection is preventable and 13(1.6%) perceived HBV infection to be the same as malaria. In terms of the perceived seriousness of HBV infection, majority of the respondents (50.2%) perceived HBV infection as a serious infection while 34(4.3%) could not tell the severity of HBV infection.

Table 3: Perceptions of students about Hepatitis B

n=794		
Variables	Frequency	Percentage
HBV is treatable	506	63.7
HBV is not treatable	200	25.2
Can be gotten from sex	569	71.4
Serious as HIV/AIDS	42	5.3
It is preventable	615	77.4
Serious as malaria	13	1.6
Not preventable	109	13.7
Perceived seriousness of HBV		
Less serious	102	12.8
Serious	398	50.2
Very serious	260	32.7
Don't know	34	4.3

Risk factors associated with HBV infection

Table 4 below shows the various predisposing factors identified by respondents to be associated with HBV infection. Having unprotected sex with an infected person was the most identified risk factor for HBV (70.8%). At least 50% of the respondents also identified the transmission of unscreened blood as a risk factor of HBV infection. In terms of preventive practices, use of condoms during sexual intercourse was the most identified preventive practice (71%) against HBV.

Table 4: Risk factors associated with HBV infection

n=794		
Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Identify risk factor*		
Unscreened blood	397	50.0
Age	116	14.6
Contact with infected person	247	31.1
Unprotected sex with infected person	562	70.8
Preventive practices of HBV*		

Abstinence from unsafe sex	264	33.2
Avoid contact with body fluid	280	35.3
Regular hospital screening	126	15.9
Use of condoms for sex	564	71.0

***Multiple responses allowed**

Discussion

We carried out this representative study to determine the knowledge of HBV among undergraduates in the University. This group is made up of a larger population of the young generation with tendencies of exploring. Results from this study identified general good knowledge of HBV infection in the study area as over 90% of the respondents had heard about HBV infection with the highest sources of information being from school and family/friends. Most of the respondents 85.4% could identify the virus to be responsible for HBV infection. This good knowledge about Hepatitis B etiology from various sources to respondents is a welcome one as researches have shown that poor knowledge of a health issue and its course may increase the prevalence of the disease. Since knowledge is a critical component of behavior change, knowing the cause of Hepatitis B virus infection is instrumental in reducing the burden of the disease and increasing health. Findings from this section of the study are slightly inconsistent with reports from the work of Okonkwo et al. (2017) which sought to determine knowledge of HBV infection in Lagos, Nigeria. Their findings showed that only 58.7% of respondents had heard about Hepatitis B, 31.5% knew that it was a viral infection and less than a third knew about its modes of transmission. This represented a moderate knowledge of HBV as against the high knowledge of HBV in this study. Variation in knowledge from this present study may be a result of the choice of the study population in the sense that this study's respondents were undergraduates who get most of their information from school and are more likely to have access to the internet. On the other hand, study respondents of Okonkwo et al. (2017) were traders whose literacy levels may not afford them access to enough information. Also, this study was consistent with a study by Al-Maweri et al. (2015) who found a good level of knowledge of HBV among undergraduate dental students in the Al-Farabi College for Dentistry and Nursing, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. This study was also consistent with findings by Osei, Niyilapah and Kofi Amenuvegbe (2019) who found that the majority (73.9%) of undergraduates of the University of Health and Allied Sciences, Ghana had good knowledge regarding HBV infection.

Besides a good number of the respondents knew that HBV infection is transmissible and could be transmitted by sharing of unsterilized sharp objects with infected persons and through unprotected sexual intercourse. The study also showed that most of the respondents knew that vaccination, the use of condoms, and proper disposal of medical waste could aid in preventing HBV infection. This finding concurs with the fact that most of the students had already indicated good knowledge of the infection and owing to an awareness campaign on HBV organized at intervals by medical students in the university, there was an expected increased level of knowledge about HBV by respondents. Findings from this section also agree with results from the study by Chingle et al. (2017) which showed that the majority of undergraduate respondents were aware of HBV infection.

Most of the respondents perceived HBV infection as treatable and over 77% agreed that it could be prevented. A good number of respondents knew that HBV can be contracted from unprotected sexual intercourse. The perception of individuals on any health matter, in most cases, informs their attitudes and health-seeking behavior about the same matter. This is such that the students who have a positive perception of a health-related matter will be more likely to take necessary measures to stay safe and healthy. The high perception of HBV virus as being treatable may inform those who feel they have the infection or those who have been diagnosed to seek adequate treatment and; those who perceived HBV to be transmissible through sexual intercourse may take up practices such as the use of condoms during sexual intercourse that will keep them safe. This finding is consistent with the study by Chingle et al. (2017) where there was a 76.8% risk perception of the Hepatitis B virus. Our study also revealed that a good number of the respondents perceived HBV infection as a serious infection with a few perceiving HBV as a less serious health issue. This section in line with the perceived severity construct of the health belief model (HBM) which holds that individuals are

more likely to take up a health service, change behavior or seek care depending on how severe they perceive a health matter to be. This however means that the respondents who perceived HBV infection as a very serious one will most likely take safety measures against the infection and seek care when they feel sick.

Findings further showed that though over 70% of the students knew about HBV vaccination, only 346(43.6%) had been vaccinated. Reasons given for low uptake of HBV vaccination included poor awareness of the HBV vaccination, cost of vaccination, and an attitude that presents HBV vaccination as not useful. This finding is consistent with the findings of Osei et al. (2019) who reported low uptake of HBV vaccination among undergraduates to be majorly associated with the perceived cost of vaccination. Our study also revealed that the transmission and use of unscreened blood and unprotected sex with infected persons were indicated by most respondents as risk factors of HBV infection. Age was also seen as a factor by few respondents. The need for blood screening before transfusion had progressed from just screening for compatibility to screening to detect infections that are blood traceable including HBV and HIV. The age of individuals was similarly implicated as a risk factor of HBV in a study by Olayinka et al. (2016). This association was described to be as a result of the weak immune systems of the neonate and the elderly. This finding however contrasts the finding by Anaedobe et al. (2015) who found the association between age and HBV to be a result of early sexual debut.

Furthermore, most of the respondents implicated contacts with infected persons as a risk factor of the infection. The need for abstinence from unprotected sexual intercourse and the use of condoms for sexual intercourse had been stressed as a means of not just preventing HBV infection, but also preventing other sexually transmitted diseases including HIV. Findings from this section of the study shed light on the modes of transmission of HBV as outlined by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention in 2018 which included sex with an infected person, contact with open sores of an infected person, and use of contaminated piercing instruments for manicure/pedicure, acupuncture and body piercings. The findings from this section are consistent with studies by Abeje and Azage (2015) and Andersson et al. (2015) which revealed exposure to sores of infected persons and the incorrect/ inconsistent use of condoms during sexual intercourse as risk factors of Hepatitis B virus infection.

In conclusion, Hepatitis B remains a major public health problem globally. Knowledge in this research study referred to the ability of an individual to understand and have a learning experience that will help them recognize HBV infection as well as its risks and transmission. Since knowledge is a critical component of behavior change, a good knowledge of HBV infection and route of transmission, as well as adequate vaccination may reduce infection rate and constitute the cornerstone for preventing transmission.

We determined the knowledge level of respondents about Hepatitis B virus infection and their perceptions towards HBV. We also determined the knowledge of risk factors associated with Hepatitis B virus infection as well as the preventive practices of the infection. The outcome of the study showed that there was an overall good knowledge of HBV infection. Despite this, a few of the respondents viewed HBV infection as less serious, and more than half of the respondents could not identify age as a risk factor of HBV infection. Based on the findings from this research, the following recommendations have been made:

- There is a need for properly planned education by health workers to students, where the need for vaccination as a means of prevention will be emphasised and where the risk factors of HBV infection will be carefully explained.
- There is a need for improved strategies in the use of social media as a means of awareness on HBV as most respondents indicated social media as their source of information.
- There should be proper education on the pathogenesis of HBV
- Encouragement on the use of condoms during sexual intercourse since this was the most identified known means of HBV infection prevention.
- On-campus social marketing campaigns encouraging testing and preventive practices are recommended.

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